

1 **NLRP2 induction during resistance to chemotherapy in human cancer.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 NLR family receptors of the innate immune system as classically defined by the ability to recognize a
7 ligand of specific composition and structure. We have described functions for NLRP10 in detection of
8 changes in speed of the cell (as an acceleration or velocity sensor), suggesting that NLR sensors might
9 possess the ability to detect and respond to composite changes in the cellular state rather than strict
10 structurally based ligand detection of a pathogen associated molecular pattern We describe here
11 activation of *NLRP2* during the chemotherapeutic treatment of humans with cancer and in response to
12 chemotherapeutic agents in vitro. NLRP2 induction was among the most prominent changes
13 transcriptome -wide both in humans with HER2+ breast cancer, and in an in vitro model of resistance to
14 chemotherapeutic agents in cultured triple negative breast cancer cells. We suggest pattern recognition
15 receptors encoded by the NLR family have the ability to recognize components of a cellular program,
16 acute changes in cellular homeostasis associated with any number of biologic parameter, like genomic
17 instability or a rapid increase in speed of the cell cycle.